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Relevance of Marital Counseling in Some Selected Churches in the Context of 1 Corinthians 7:1-5

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Abstract

Marriage counseling is as old as marriage itself. It is introduced to guide the couples how to have successful marriages and live happily yet the rate of divorce is increasing daily. This work considered the relevance of marriage counseling in some selected Churches in the context of 1 Corinthians 7: 1-7 the findings revealed that sexual incapability in marriage is still visible due to couple's noncompliance to biblical standard of marriage for peaceful homes, other factors are lack of continued love, pressure from the family, low income or economy situation, above all infidelity and marital bully from each side can lead to marital problem. The study adopted the descriptive and exegetical method of the survey type. simple percentage, while responses to the interview were qualitatively analyzed. Finding revealed that marriage crisis was all over the place and that Methodist Church Nigeria Diocese Mainland is not left out. The study concluded that adopting 1 Corinthians 7:1-7 as the basis for some selected Churches will enhance the peaceful co-existence among the couples in the Churches and society at large. The study recommended that Church should take cognizes of Paul' teaching in 1 Corinthians 7:1-7 in marriage for peaceful co-existence.

Keywords: Relevance, Marriage, Counseling, Church, 1 Corinthians 7:1-7

Introduction

The first letter of Paul to the Corinthians chapter seven addresses a number of issues that had come to the attention of Paul through reports from some of the members of the Church and apparently a letter from the Church in which they had asked the apostle certain questions. A cursive glance at the chapter reveals that in their prevailing circumstances, some Christians were concerned about whether or not it was good to have sexual relations with woman (1 Cor 7:1). Others had issues with whether to continue in marriage with an unbeliever (1 Cor 7:10-11) and perhaps, anxiety about the spiritual status with the children of unbelieving partners.¹ There is almost a general consensus among scholars that 1 Corinthians 7 deals with questions and concerns the believers in Corinth had about marriage, sex and related issues. The background of the believers in Corinth lies in a variety of religious and philosophical beliefs and practices is established. This variety certainly influenced their concept of spirituality. No wonder, among the factors accounting for the differences within the Church was the concept of spirituality. Paul's response to some of the questions having to do with marriage and related issues including sex. What made these issues matters of concern can be gleaned from Paul's response, which is believed to reflect the concerns of the Corinthians Christians (1 Cor 7:14).

The creator Himself declared that it was not good for the man be alone (Gen 2:18) yet no creature on earth could be found that was suitable partner for him (2:20b). Dogs, cats, parrots, horses, snakes, fish, etc., all these creatures of the animal world have become pets of

mankind, but a pampered pet is not an equal partner. So in the beginning God made a helper corresponding to the man, this new creature was perfectly suited to the man, for the woman was taken from the man, assuring the uniqueness, the ministry and the permanence of their relationship. The approval by God of this first relationship is vivified by the statement that the Lord himself brought the woman to the man, the detail narrative describing, the creation of the woman underscores her significance in God's purpose in creation.

Marriages a mystical and intimate union instituted and ordained by God with purpose of companionship and oneness. It is a sacred and permanent union that only death can dissolve. This is because as through marriage the man and the woman freely and willingly decide to spend the rest of their lives on earth together (Augustine, 1999).

Therefore, the covenant of marriage glues, unites and ties their hearts and live together. In respect of the filial duty, marriage is the merging of two different personalities, that is a man and a woman into an indissoluble union through covenant, as an ordained institution by God, marriage is the deepest corporeal and spiritual unity of a man and a woman.

Marriage is the foundation of human society because it is the first institution that was created by God. The stability of the human society depends on the stability of the marriage institution. An unstable marriage is capable of affecting every strata of life of an individual and his/her society, marriage was established by God before all other human institutions. This shows us that marriage is the foundation of human society. In God's plan, marriage is the basis for a morally and socially stable society. This is part of the reason why God hates adultery (Ex. 20:14), sexual immorality (1 Thes 4:3-6), incest (Lev. 18-6ft), and opined that "Marriage is not easy to define because of the diversities in the system of marriage throughout the world. Different scholars have defined marriage in different ways". Fagbeyibo (2005) stressed that marriage is "A relationship of one or more men, with one or more women, which is recognized by custom or law and which involves certain rights and duties, both in the case of parties entering the union and in the case of the children" One can deduce from the above definition that marriage recognized as such by society, according to its own rules, which could vary from place to place. However, such casual sexual relationships or even stable relationships as in the case of a man and a woman just living together are excluded. Certain obligations and requirements must be met especially as marriage involves the conceiving and bringing up children. And there are different types of marriage, such as customary or traditional marriage, religious marriage, ordinance or court marriage etc.

"Every culture in the world has its own set of customs and rules concerning marriage, sex and family. However, since it was God who created mankind as male and female and since it was God who joined the first man and woman together in marriage, it is very important for us to understand what God has to say about marriage, sex and the family" To Wright, "marriage is the state in which men and women can live together in sexual relationship with the approval of their social group"

The above definitions of marriage illustrate its dual nature as both a public institution and private personal relationship. On the other hand, marriage involves an emotional and sexual relationship between particular human beings. On the other hand, marriage is an institution that transcends the particular individual involved in it and unites two families.

Different people perceive marriage differently. "The customary belief is that marriage is primarily contracted to raise children. In-Laws, neighbours and friends are usually unkind

to couples who have no child. The other dimension is the sex of the child. The clamour for male

Child in our society has affected even Christians. Mothers who have given birth to only female children are usually on edge whenever they are pregnant. Will it be a boy or a girl? Childlessness and having only female children contribute significant to the high rate of divorce and polygamy” (Timothy, 2010).

Who gives children, and who is responsible for the sex of the child? Often, it is the woman who is blamed for lack of children and giving birth only to females. Yet children are the heritage of the Lord (Ps 127:3). They cannot be bought in market. God gives them and determines their sex too. Although medically the male sperm that fertilizes the female egg determines the sex of the child. Christian knows that, God is at work, thus the woman is not the determinant of the child gender, is what the man deposited in her, she brings out.

In some subcultures, marriage connects two families in a complicated set of property exchanges involving land, labour and other resources. The extended family and society also share an interest in any children the couple may have. Furthermore, the legal and religious definitions of marriage and the laws that surround it usually represent the symbolic expression of core cultural norms (informal behavioral guidelines) and values. It is on this note that, Ubong E. Eyo, 2021 points out that “marriage is a complex affair with social, emotional and religious (though sometimes with economic and political) undertones with often overlap so firmly that each undertone cannot be separated from each other”.

Among Africans in particular, marriage is not only for the living, it is a union where the living, the dead and the yet unborn meet. Hence, John Mbiti says “It is the point where all members of the community meet; the departed, the living and those yet unborn”. Marriage is therefore, a duty, a requirement from the corporate society and a rhythm of life in which everyone must participate.

The Old Testament Theology of Sexuality

The first two chapters of the Bible deal directly with the question of human sexuality. Not only is human sexuality presented as a basic fact of Creation, but elucidating the nature of sexuality constitutes a central part of the Creation accounts.

A clear understanding of these basic statements is crucial, since here “the pattern is established and adjudged good. From then until the close of the biblical corpus it is the assumed norm.” In Genesis 1:26-28 “the highpoint and goal has been reached toward which all of God’s creativity from verse 1 on was directed.” Discussion among theologians over this passage has largely focused on the meaning of humans being created in the “image of God” and has almost entirely ignored the further affirmation that humankind is created male and female.” The fundamental insights into the theology of human sexuality from Genesis 1:1-24 come under seven subheadings.

- i. *Creation Order*: In the clause concerning the creation of humans as male and female (Genesis 1:27), sexual differentiation is presented as a creation by God, and not part of the divine order. Throughout the mythology of the ancient Near East, the sexual activities of the gods form a dominant motif. In the fertility cults, creation was often celebrated resulting from the union of male and female deities. In contrast, Genesis 1: with its emphasis upon the transcendent God (Elohim) and a cosmic view of creation, posits a radical separation of sexuality and divinity.

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- God stands “absolutely beyond the polarity of sex.” The sexual distinctions are presented as created by God, not part of the divine order.
- ii. *A duality from the beginning:* The sexual distinction between male and female is fundamental to what it means to be human. To be human is to live as a sexual person. The sexual distinction is presented in Genesis 1 as a basic component in the original creation of humankind.
 - iii. *Equality of the sexes:* A third insight into the theology of human sexuality stems from the equal pairing of male and female in parallel with Adam in Genesis 1:27. There is no hint of superiority or inferiority between male and female. Both are “equally immediate to the Creator and His act.” Both are given the same dominion over the earth and other living creatures (verses 26 and 28). Both are to share alike in the blessing and responsibility of procreation (verse 28). Both participate equally in the image of God.
 - iv. *Wholeness:* A fourth theological insight will serve to bridge our discussion from “male and female” to the image of God (*imago Dei*). In Genesis 1:27 the generic term for humankind (Adam) includes both male and female. The holistic picture of humankind is only complete when male and female are viewed together. Such a description points the individuality and complementarity of the sexes.
 - v. *Relationship:* The juxtaposition of male and female in Genesis 1:26 intimates what will become explicit in Genesis 2: the full meaning of human existence not in male or female in isolation, but in their mutual communion.
 - vi. *Procreation:* From Genesis 1:28, one of the primary purposes of sexuality is procreation, as indicated in the words, “Be fruitful and multiply”. Procreation is shown to be part of the divine design. This divine blessing or command is to be taken seriously and acted upon freely and responsibly in the power that attends God’s blessing. Nevertheless, sexuality cannot be wholly subordinated to the intent to propagate children. Sexual differentiation has meaning apart from the procreative purpose. The procreative blessing is also pronounced upon the birds and fish (verse 22), but only humans are made in the image of God. Genesis 1: emphasizes that sexual distinction in humankind is created by God, particularly for fellowship, for relationship, between male and female.
 - vii. *Wholeness and beauty:* When God saw everything that He made was good, including the sexuality of his crowning work of Creation (Genesis 1:31). Including the act of sexual intercourse which was part of God’s creation, part of his crowning act. Therefore, declares the first chapter of Genesis, sex is good, very good. It is not a mistake, a sinful aberration, a “regrettable necessity” a shameful experience, as it has so often been regarded in the history of Christian as well as pagan thought. Rather, human sexuality is divinely inaugurated; it was part of God’s perfect design from the beginning, a fundamental aspect of human existence.
 - viii. *Finding completeness:* Because man was created first, it has been asserted that “by this the priority and superiority of the man, and the dependence of the woman upon the man, are established as an ordinance of divine creation.” But the movement in Genesis 2 is not from superior to inferior, but from incompleteness to completeness. Woman is created as the climax to culminate of the story and she is the crowning work of creation.

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- ix. *Sexuality as wholeness:* The holistic view presented in Genesis 2:7 mean that human sexuality cannot be compartmentalized into “the things of the body” versus “the things of the spirit or soul.” Human beings are sexual creatures, and their sexuality is manifested in every aspect of human existence. Genesis 2: opens with the creation of man. But creation is not finished for the man was alone and incomplete. But this was not good (Verse 18). Man needs a helper or benefactor who is his counterpart. Thus, begins man’s quest to satisfy his God’s installed “hunger for wholeness.” Such hunger is not satisfied by his animal companions, but by the sexual being God has built or made to be alongside him as his complement. Adam in effect exclaims at his first sight of Eve, “At last. I am whole! Here is the complement of myself.
- x. *A multidimensional relationship:* Closely connected with “complementary wholeness’ is the idea of relationship. If Genesis 1: whispers that human sexuality is for fellowship and for relationship, Genesis 2 orchestrates this act with a volume of double forte, and the melody and harmony of the narrative portray richness and beauty in the relational symphony of the sexes. In Genesis 2, the creation of Eve takes place in a context of loneliness. The keynote is struck in verse 18: “It is not good that the man should be alone...” This passage may be seen to affirm the various mutual social relationships that should take place between the sexes, but more specifically the Genesis account links the concept of sodality to the manage relationship.

Concept of Sex within Marriage

- i. *Sex Was Created by God and Is Good:* When he created human beings, God made us male and female and declared that his creation was good. He instructed the first husband and wife to “be fruitful and increase in number” instructions that clearly involved nakedness and sexual intercourse (Genesis 1:27-28; 2:24-25). This was not something considered shameful or at best tolerated by God, but rather sex is evidence of God’s goodness. It is something for which we can express praise and gratitude.
- ii. *Sex Is for Propagation and Pleasure:* The first birth recorded in the Bible is described as a result of sexual intercourse plus “the help of the Lord” (Genesis 4:1). Obviously, sex is involved in the conception of children and in the divine command to multiply. In the New Testament, we read that a husband and wife are depriving one another when they refuse to give physical pleasure and satisfaction to each other. The only exception to this is when a married couple agrees to abstain from sex temporarily and for the purpose of retreating spiritually for a special time of prayer (Matthew 19:4-6; 1Corinthians 7:5).
- iii. *Sex Is for Marriage:* Whenever the Bible speaks approvingly about sex, it refers to married couples. Quoting Genesis, Jesus spoke with favor about the permanence and “one flesh” nature of marriage. Paul noted that marriage (not intercourse outside of marriage) is the desirable answer for a person who is struggling with sexual self-control. When marriage occurs, the husband and wife are to give their bodies freely to each other and not hold back sexually.
- iv. *Sexual Immorality Is Condemned Strongly:* Sexual looseness may be tolerated in our society, but it is condemned with vehemence in the Bible. God, who created sex,

has commanded us to abstain from sexual immorality. This is not because God wants to take away our fun. It is because the Creator knows the dangers of sexual abuse and wants to protect us from the misery that comes when we give in to lustful passions and accept the self-centered sexual values of people who neither know nor respect God's Word. Adultery is pictured in the Bible as something very attractive that ultimately is destructive and foolish.

Sexual Problems within Marriage

Probably most people approach marriage with enthusiasm about the sexual freedom that will follow. Many of these same people are disappointed when they discover (sometimes as early as the honeymoon) that sex within marriage is not as consistently exciting or pleasurable as they had hoped or expected. There are numerous causes for this.

- i. *Misinformation:* Despite the modern openness about sex, counselors often are amazed at the ignorance and lack of accurate knowledge that is characteristic of many couples. Sex researcher William Masters has concluded that "the greatest cause of sexual problems is misinformation, misconception, and taboo
- ii. *Cultural Attitudes:* The society in which one lives often molds sexual attitudes and behavior. In past decades sex was not discussed openly in our culture, and marital fidelity was the expected norm. Some people considered sex to be dirty, a taboo subject for polite society, something that interested men, but was of little concern to women who were assumed to be passive and lacking in sexual interest or arousal. Attitudes like these may have contributed to the relatively low frequency of intercourse apart from marriage, but they also must have created misunderstanding and sexual frustration.
- iii. *Stress:* Recently an experienced sex therapist was asked to list some sexual problems that have become more apparent during the past fifteen years. It is surprising perhaps that "lack of desire" came at the top of the list. One big cause of lack of desire today is stress, the counselor added. Many people invest so much energy and time into their jobs that they feel drained and want to be left alone. When work creates anxiety, concern over job security or fear of business reversals, interest in love making declines, partly because of physical reasons. In men, for example, prolonged stress sharply decreases the level of testosterone, the primary male hormone.
- iv. *Fatigue, Haste, and Lack of Opportunity:* Fatigue is a common cause of unsatisfactory sex. Mutually pleasurable sexual intercourse takes physical and mental energy. It also takes a relaxed, unhurried attitude that is not greatly concerned about time. When a young couple is first married, they can sleep late on weekends, and have no children to demand their attention, to interrupt their love making, or to interfere with sexual spontaneity. These couples often have a great deal of vigor and natural energy. As they grow older, the husband and wife may have an undiminished desire for sex, but they also have less energy, more responsibilities and demands on their time, increased mental or physical fatigue, and a need for more sleep.
- v. *Boredom:* After a couple has been married for a while, they get accustomed to each other. They run out of novel ways to have sex, foreplay becomes shorter, and coitus becomes routine. After several years, the sexual activities that once

were so exciting have become monotonous. Partners spend little time stimulating each other sexually, and sometimes the husband and wife become less interested in their appearance. Sex under such circumstances is not very fulfilling to say the least, and the stage has been set for an extramarital experience with someone who is more exciting and novel than one's mate (Familusi, 1976).

- vi. *Physical Causes:* Sometimes sexual problems have physical origins such as endocrine disturbances, obesity, diabetes, low energy level, or the weakening of vaginal muscles in women who have given birth. Sometimes a physical illness prevents sexual behavior, and at other times it may cause people to be afraid of intercourse. In one research study, for example, it was found that 80 percent of heart attack patients were afraid to resume sexual activity after their illness, and 42 percent of the men had difficulties attaining and maintaining an erection. Almost and always, when physiology creates sexual problems, psychological tensions come as well and a vicious circular develops, the physiological problem creates psychological tension that in turn hinders physical functioning. In some cases, physiological malfunctioning is used as an excuse for abstinence or sexual difficulties.

Effects of Sexual Problems within Marriage

When sexual problems appear, some couples simply give up and don't try to resolve their difficulties. There may be fear of discussing the frustrations or a belief that things will never get better. Others develop physical symptoms, such as headache, abdominal pain, fatigue, or emotional distress, all of which hide the sexual problem and provide an excuse for abstinence.

In addition to the avoidance of intercourse, sexual difficulties in marriage can lead to several major effects:

- i. *Inability to Perform.* Numerous books and research reports have described the symptoms and causes of the more common sexual problems in marriage. These include orgasmic dysfunction (more often known as frigidity, a condition in which the female is unable or unwilling to experience full sexual pleasure including orgasm), vaginismus (a condition in which the vaginal entrance closes tightly when penetration is attempted), erectile dysfunction (also known as impotence, the inability of a male to achieve or maintain an erection), premature ejaculation (the ejaculation of semen, with a resulting loss of erection, immediately before, just at, or shortly after insertion of the penis into the vagina), retarded ejaculation (the opposite of premature ejaculation this occurs when the penis remains erect but ejaculation does not occur), and dyspareunia (painful intercourse). While each of these may have a physical basis, the cause can also be psychological (Ike, 2005).
- ii. *Lowered Self-Esteem.* Self-esteem and sexual capability often go together, especially in men. If intercourse is not mutually satisfying, the husband and wife may both have doubts about their sexual competence, doubts that sometimes are accentuated by the joking of one's mate. If a man cannot maintain an erection or arouse his wife, for example, he is likely to experience a loss of confidence about his sexual and manly capabilities. If his wife jokes about the fact that he may be

losing his virility, this is an even greater blow to his self-esteem, and his ability to perform sexually is hindered further.

- iii. *Selection of Substitutes.* When sex within marriage is not satisfying, husbands and wives often turn to substitute activities. These include masturbation, or extramarital sex which often comes as a result of sexual problems within marriage, but instead of the hoped-for fulfillment, affairs can often lead to guilt, concerns about secrecy, and further marital, sexual, and personal frustration.

New American standard Bible	Nestle Alland 27 th Edition
But because of immoralities, each man is to have his own wife, and each woman is to have her own husband.	διὰ δὲ τὰς πορνείας ἕκαστος τὴν ἑαυτοῦ γυναῖκα ἔχεται καὶ ἕκαστη τὸν ἴδιον ἄνδρα ἔχεται

One is not surprised about the conclusion of the scholars who interpret “to touch as meaning’ to marry”, because it is only logical for them to conclude that *ἐχέτω* (have) would mean to get married. Consequently, it is not surprising that they concluded in this verse that Paul is saying that marriage is only permissible as a means of preventing sexual immorality. For example, Mare concludes that, “having said that it would be good under the present circumstances not to get married, Paul hastens to add that the general rule for marriage should apply. The reason, especially true at Corinth, is the prevalence of sexual immorality”. The correct interpretation is however as Saka,1980 also indicates that. “It is important to stress that the passage is not connected with any form of marriage but with celibacy and marriage threatened by sexual asceticism”. This assertion from Ukpong (2014) would fit in to the context as already indicated above, that if the word “touch” does not mean to marry, then it would be difficult to interpret verse two as taking about marriage, the understanding that *ἐχέτω* is also a euphemism for sex stands here also. So, the understanding of verse two would be that every man should have sexual intercourse with this wife and the woman is also to have sex with the husband. This interpretation fits the context more as it would also be revealed in the understanding of verse three to five.

Verse 3

New American standard Bible	Nestle Alland 27 th Edition
The husband must fulfill his duty to his wife, and likewise also the wife to her husband.	τῇ γυναικὶ ὁ ἀνὴρ τὴν ὀφειλὴν ἀποδιδότω, ὁμοίως δὲ καὶ ἡ γυνὴ τῷ ἀνδρὶ

The most important phrase in this verse is “*apodidoto*” which literally means “repay what is owed”. This again is another euphemism for sexual relationship between the husband and the wife. Samuel (2010) Greek Dictionary says that, figuratively the word means, obligation” or “duty” and that it is a euphemism for sexual intercourse that becomes a duty after a marriage and in this sense can also be translated conjugal duty”. A survey of various translations shows that various ways were used by the translators, but the meaning is still sexual relationship.

For example.

Bible Version	1 Corinthian 7:3
King James” Version	Let the husband render unto the wife due

	benevolence and likewise also the wife unto the husband
New International Version	The husband should fulfill his marital duty to his wife, and likewise the wife to her husband.
New American Standard Bible	The husband must fulfill his duty to his wife, and likewise also the wife to her husband.
Revised standard Version	The husband should give to his wife her conjugal rights, and likewise the wife to her husband.
The Bible in Basic English	Let the husband give to the wife what is right; and let the wife do the same to the husband.

Verse 4

New American standard Bible	Nestle Alland 27 th Edition
The wife does not have authority over her own body, but the husband does' and likewise also the husband does not have authority over his own body but the wife does.	ἡ γυνή του ἰδίου σωματος οὐκ ἐξουσιάζει ἀλλὰ ὁ ἀνὴρ, ὁμοίως δὲ καὶ ὁ ἀνὴρ τοῦ ἰδίου σώματος οὐκ ἐξουσιάζει ἀλλὰ ἡ γυνή

The key word in this verse ἐξουσιάζει which, as Paul 1975 and James 2011 indicate means having and exercising authority in its various senses; having the right or freedom to exercise authority over or having (independent) control of something. In this sense and context. Paul seems to emphasize that in a marriage situation, the independent control of one's body according to one's inclination ceases and it becomes a joint decision along with the partner.

The verse is the peak of one new teaching on sex and sexuality that Paul has introduced subtly to humanity. It is amazing that Paul did not give the man authority over the woman (neither did he give the woman authority over the man) in sexual matters. This teaching would greatly offend cultural sensibilities wherein the man is the lord of the jungle in sexual matters. For example, many people have in their subconscious minds that the woman has no right to ask for sex or imitate sex, and so women burn with passion rather than express it to their husbands. This point is also raised by Gerhard, 1961 who says that, "the sexual demands in the marriage were the same for both husband and wife. This represents a radical statement for the century-and for today's society as well".

A close examination of the build-up reveals that from verse 2, Paul had been balancing his statements in terms of gender. In verse 2 and 3, mentions the husband first, but in verse 4, he brings forth the woman to the first position knowing quite well that doing that places the emphasis on the woman. This could be interpreted for two angles first, it is the woman that is guilty of withdrawing her body from the man, usually as revenge tactics, second, it of importance in sexual matters

Building a Biblical View of Sex in Africa

Having arrived at what can be called the contextual message of 1 Corinthians 7:1-5, one can now on the basis of this postulate a biblical view of sex in African context.

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- i. *Sexual Pleasure is not the Exclusive Preserve of Men:* It has to be understood and taught that sexual pleasure is not the exclusive preserve of men and so women too should be allowed to initiate and enjoy sex as much as men do. As such the practice of female genital mutilation and all attempts so discourage women from initiating and enjoying sex have to be stopped because it is unbiblical. It has to be understood that even sexual passion is God created and every human being has the capacity and so none should be forced to suppress his or her feelings.
 - ii. *Sexual Intercourse can take Place Daily:* Apart from the periods that women are under menstruation and when there is a mutual agreement, sex can be enjoyed by both male and female. There is need for a new orientation that would change the women perception about sex, arising from culture, in Africa in order to be able to have sex regularly. This is far too important because most people are running away from being polygamous, and so they have to fulfill their sexual desire outside marriage. We must note that non-satisfaction of sexual desires is one of the major causes of extramarital affairs, which is the alternative to the no more appealing polygamy.
 - iii. *Sex is not just for Procreation:* There is the need for Africans to realize that sex is not just for the purpose of rearing children. Sex is meant to be enjoyed both parties and not just for bringing children into the world. The emphasis on children should be played down. Rushing to get pregnant immediately after marriage is one of the things that destiny the intimacy a couple has to build together.
 - iv. *Sex is not Sin:* There is nothing in the Bible to suggest that sex is sinful. Sex is a God-given gift that has to be used within God's own prescribed boundaries and it is only when sex takes place outside God's instruction that it becomes a sin.
 - v. *Sex is not a tool for Vengeance:* Most often than not both the man and woman use sex a tool for vengeance so that the spouse can be taught a lesson There are times when people abstain from sex just because they want to deal with their spouse, as Wright (1973) opined For example, a woman may refuse to have sex with her husband because the husband has not provided her the money she has asked for or a man may refrain from sex just because the wife is nagging (Familusi, 2014).
 - vi. *Abstaining from sex for spiritual reasons is 'Pseudo-Spirituality':* Trying to avoid sex because one wants to be holy or draw closer to God is a form of pseudo-spirituality. It has to be noted that there are people who want to avoid their conjugal responsibility under the guise of serving God. These types of people have to be taught that taking care of one's conjugal responsibility is in itself a spiritual service and that neglecting it does not make one's service acceptable to God (Allan, 1969).

Conclusion and Recommendations

There is no doubt in the assertion that the family is the main source of security for individuals, however, families are faced with varying challenges and problems in the present modern societies which affects their marital relationships and satisfaction. Methodist church Nigeria, Diocese of Lagos Mainland which has been the focused of the work have shown strict adherence to biblical teachings on marriage through the culture of a robust family counseling.

The paper based on the findings recommends that:

Counselors especially those trained by the church should focus on strengthening marital relationship through addressing role conflicts, enhancing life skills, and helping to foster wellness and resiliency to cope with factors leading to marital crises and divorce

In addition to that the spiritual leaders of Methodist Church Nigeria, Diocese of Lagos Mainland should regularly organize marriage counseling symposia, seminars, workshops for their married members to address career-related issues and them promote marital well-being.

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